

Characterisation of fibre/matrix interfacial fracture energy using the single fibre peel experiment

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Contents

- Motivation
- Introduction of fibre peel experiment
- Fracture mechanics based analysis and requirements
- Experimental setup and data processing
- Preliminary results
- Challenges and outlook

Motivation

- Controlling the behaviour at macro scale requires understanding at the micro scale.
 - Macro: delamination, fibre bridging etc.
 - Micro: fibre, matrix and fibre/matrix interface.
- Characterisation of the fibre/matrix interface.
- Current micromechanical experiments focus on shear type failure (mode II).
 - Microbond, single fibre fragmentation, fibre pull- or push-out.

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Single fibre peel experiment

- Introduced by Alimuddin and Piggott in the 90s [1].
- Forgotten/abandoned?

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Analysis method

Energy release rate of beam under pure moments [2]:

$$J = \frac{M^2}{2BEI}$$

Where E is the Young's modulus, B is the beam width and I is the second moment of area.

For a fibre: $B = 2r$ and $I = \frac{\pi}{4}r^4$

From classical beam theory we have:

$$M = \frac{EI}{R}$$

Analysis method

We assume a perfectly half-embedded fibre (i.e. $H_e = r$), such that the fracture area:

$$dA = \pi r da$$

Next, we set the energy release to be equal to the energy consumed:

$$JBda = \pi r G_c da$$

Isolating G_c and inserting previous equations:

$$G_c = \frac{Er^3}{8R^2}$$

Requirements to determine G_c

$$G_c = \frac{Er^3}{8R^2}$$

- Fibre modulus, E
- Fibre radius, r
- Radius of curvature, R
 - Near crack tip
 - When fracture initiates

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Experimental setup

- Sample preparation at University of Strathclyde (Glass fibre/vinyl ester).
- In situ SEM observation of a single fibre being peeled out of resin.

Example video

Feature extraction and analysis

Fig. 1: Still image of fibre undergoing peel, obtained by SEM

Fig. 2: Extraction of fibre feature

$$\frac{1}{R(x)} = \frac{|y''(x)|}{[1 + (y'(x))^2]^{3/2}}$$

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Preliminary results

- Two samples tested successfully before breakdown of fixture
- Same sample may be tested multiple times

Sample	Meas. No.	Radius of curvature [m]	Fibre radius r [μm]	Fracture energy G_c [J/m^2]
S3-02	1	7e-4	8.1	9
S3-02	2	6e-4	8.1	14
S3-02	3	8e-4	8.1	8
S3-03	4	12e-4	8.1	3
S3-03	5	14e-4	8.1	2

Are we in the right ballpark?

- Interfacial fracture energy found to be 2-14 J/m² for glass fibre/vinyl ester interfaces.
- Very limited sample size.
- Only considering moment i.e. under estimating fracture toughness
- Broadly comparable to results by Liechti and Chai [3] for glass/epoxy interfaces (4-36 J/m²), depending on phase angle.
- Original single fibre peel experiment by Alimuddin and Piggot [1] concluded interface toughness of 140±50 J/m² for glass/epoxy.

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Challenges

- Manufacturing: control of embeddedness
 - Checking embeddedness
- Sample handling and mounting in SEM
- Recording experiment in SEM with high framerate
- Determining crack tip location
- Consistent fitting

Summary and outlook

- Demonstration of concept, not quite a proof yet.
- Interfacial fracture energy determined using the radius of curvature, fibre radius and Young's modulus.
- Future work to include non-linear beam theory (fibre bridging model).
- Testing of various material systems.

Acknowledgements

Special thanks to research technician Erik Vogeley and DACOMAT partners:

References

- [1] Alimuddin M and Piggott M 1999 *Polym. Compos.* **20** 655-663
- [2] Rice J R 1968 *J App. Mech.* **35** 379-386
- [3] Liechti K M and Chai Y S 1992 *J. Appl. Mech. Trans. ASME* **59** 295-304